

Kullback-Leibler divergences: what might those numbers mean?

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The Kullback-Leibler divergence provides a numerical measure of how similar two distributions are. But once you have a number – e.g. 0.03 – how similar is that in some real-world sense? For example, is that number like that obtained for some sort of badly-sampled Gaussian – and if so ... how badly sampled? Here I present some benchmarks to help the ordinary physicist get an indication of how distribution similarity varies for a range of Kullback-Leibler divergences.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence [1, 2] provides a numerical measure of how similar two distributions are. But how similar is that? Here I present some simple benchmarks to aid the non-specialist in getting an indication what degree of similarity a divergence of (e.g.) 0.03 might indicate – as indeed might be the case for any other value. Of course if we were to compare three or more distributions, then any numerical benchmarking is usually unnecessary – we can just select the closest match, or simply rank them.

The idea here is that I decide on a specific reference distribution, then compare the KL divergence between this “perfect” distribution and some numerically generated distributions derived from that perfect distribution, but with vaying degrees of sampling. As we gradually increase the sampling, we will see how the KL divergence then decreases, gives us a sense of how matched the distributions are in terms of a sampling density. In what follows I will consider the rectangular (“top-hat”), Gaussian (aka normal), Laplacian (double exponential), and Log-normal distributions.

II. KULLBACK-LEIBLER DIVERGENCE

Mathematically, the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence [1, 2], usually denoted D_{KL} , is an indication of statistical distance. That is, it is a metric for how much an approximating probability distribution Q is from a target or “true” probability distribution P .

For our purposes here we consider two probability distributions, a P which represents some actual data or observations, and another Q which represents a theory or model of that data. Given this, the KL divergence is

$$D_{\text{KL}}(P||Q) = \sum_{x \in X} P(x) \log \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)}. \quad (1)$$

Here, in order to draw some general lessons, I use synthetic data with fully controllable properties. Thus the P distributions will be histograms generated from numerically sampling from specified distributions; i.e. not real-world experimental data.

III. SAMPLING DENSITY EFFECTS

Although in a sense the KL divergence between two distributions is self explanatory, given the formula used to compute it, the simple number it returns does really provide an

FIG. 1. KL divergences as a function of sampling density S for the Rectangular distribution. Results for a range of bin-counts are given, as indicated by the increasing symbol sizes, for counts $2^m = 32, 256, 1024$.

everyday sense of that similarity. This document attempts to provide such a benchmarking.

The idea is to decide on a specific reference distribution Q , then compare the KL divergence between this reference distribution and some numerically generated histogram-distributions P derived from that perfect distribution, but with vaying degrees of sampling, and varying histogram bin-widths. By gradually increasing the sampling, and seeing how the KL divergence decreases gives us a sense of how divergence values correspond to these differences between distributions. Later, in section IV, I will also compare intentionally mismatched distributions.

Note that in order to generate or evaluate this progression, I have somewhat reversed the sense of the P -as-data and Q -as-model given above; here, at least to start with, the model distribution Q will indeed be the underlying behaviour approached as observations of P get ever better sampled.

A. Numerics

When generating the histograms (distributions) for P I define the span to cover as from -8 to $+8$ standard deviations, breaking that range into 2^m evenly spaced bins, where I allow m to span the range $m \in \{1, \dots, 10\}$. This means that there are $2^m + 1$ breakpoints between bins, and 2^m bin midpoints.

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FIG. 2. KL divergences as a function of sampling density S for the sampled Gaussian and Gaussian+L distributions, as compared against a pure Gaussian model. Results for a range of bin-counts are given, as indicated by the increasing symbol sizes, for counts $2^m = 32, 256, 1024$.

For each value of m I then generate 2^n samples from our three distributions, where $n \in \{4, \dots, 2^{11+m}\}$. These are then binned according to the breakpoints I have defined. The small number of out-of-range sample values, i.e those outside ± 8 standard deviations are discarded. Barring this small fraction of discards, this means that for an example case for some m and n , the average number of samples per bin is $S = 2^{n-m}$.

Lastly, for simplicity, the model distribution Q is simply obtained by evaluating its functional form at the bin midpoints; rather than the exact value that would be obtained by integrating across the intervals between the bin breakpoints. This approximation is unlikely to be significant except at coarse bins sizes, and not in the fine-resolution limiting case which is my primary interest here.

The script that implements this algorithm is written in the R statistical/graphical language [3], with the help of the extraDistr [4] and philentropy [5] packages; the philentropy one containing the KL implementation.

B. Results

The four distributions I choose as ideal “model” distributions are the rectangular, the Gaussian, the Laplacian, and the Log-normal.

After sampling the distributions for each combination in our parameter ranges, I plot on fig. 1, 2, 3, and 4 how the KL divergence decreases as the sampling improves. Notably, at the extreme left, there is a “knee” in the progression as the sampling per bin increases beyond 1, followed by an essentially straight-line power-law like fall off as the sampling improves further. Further, note that the outcome is not especially dependent on bin sizes, except for the rectangular distribution, which for 32 bins finds a floor at a $\log_2(D_{KL}) \simeq 2^{-5}$. This is because the bin breakpoints are poorly aligned to the actual sharply-defined edges of the distribution.

FIG. 3. KL divergences as a function of sampling density S for the sampled Laplacian and Laplacian+G distributions, as compared against a pure Laplacian model. Results for a range of bin-counts are given, as indicated by the increasing symbol sizes, for counts $2^m = 32, 256, 1024$.

FIG. 4. KL divergences as a function of sampling density S for the sampled Log-normal distribution. Results for a range of bin-counts are given, as indicated by the increasing symbol sizes, for counts $2^m = 32, 256, 1024$.

Broadly, the lesson from figs. 2, 3, and 4 is that for the pure Gaussian, Laplacian, and Log-normal samplings, doubling of the sampling density results in a halving of the KL divergence. Our $D_{KL} = 0.03$ example number from the abstract is about $1/32$, so that it represents the similarity that would be achieved by sampling an accurate model distribution P at an average of 32 data points per bin; although as the figures indicate, this does have some dependence on the chosen bin width. One caveat here is that since I test only one sampling per parameter set, there remain minor statistical idiosyncracies in the computed KLs shown; but the dominant

trends remain unaffected.

sampling.

IV. MODEL MISMATCHES & SAMPLING

In applications we could not always expect the sampled “true” distribution to approach our model as in the simple examples above. In such cases, despite ever improving sampling densities, the KL divergence should level off at some minimum value. This minimum represents the difference between the sampled “truth” P and the proposed – and somewhat mismatched – model Q .

To do this I vary the process described above slightly: now, for every three values sampled from a primary distribution (either Gaussian or Laplacian), I sample one from the alternative (i.e. either Laplacian or Gaussian respectively). This gives us a controlled mismatch between the high-sampling limit of the numerically generated distribution and the theoretical model distribution. I denote the mainly Gaussian hybrid distribution as “Gaussian+L”, and the mainly Laplacian one as “Laplacian+G”.

We can see this effect on both figs. 2 and 3 as the sampling density S increases. For these hybrid sample distributions the KL divergence limit becomes $\log_2(D_{\text{KL}}) \simeq -6.3$ or -7.6 for the Gaussian+L and Laplacian+G respectively. The KL divergence for the Gaussian+L case has a higher floor, since the slower fall-off of the Laplacian starts to dominate away from the central core, despite its overall lesser contribution to the

V. CONCLUSION

Notably, a real-world usage might be to not only compare your experimentally measured data distribution P' to the model distribution Q , but also to compare a numerically generated distribution P – based on the model, but with an equivalent sampling to the experiment – to the model. In such a comparison, we could consider the ratio of or difference between KL divergences e.g. by defining $\Delta = D_{\text{KL}}(P||Q)/D_{\text{KL}}(P'||Q)$, to give an indication of the comparative importance of the sampling density versus that of any distribution mismatch. However, it might be best to generate an ensemble of numerical distributions P_i , and average their various $D_{\text{KL}i} = D_{\text{KL}}(P_i||Q)$ and compute the standard deviation. Then, using that averaged $D_{\text{KL}}(\bar{P}||Q)$ to compute Δ , along with the standard deviation in/of the $D_{\text{KL}i}$, could then give a sense of the statistical significance of that difference.

Other styles of benchmarks might also be investigated, such as offsets or changes in standard deviation. Of course, for those cases, varying the sampling density is not necessary, since the analytic formula is sufficient, but when considering the comparison of real data to a model distribution, the role of sampling is of key importance. We saw in figs. 2 and 3, for example, that only once we sampled above an average of 2^5 values per bin did any discrepancy between our hybrid sampling’s P and the simple model’s Q become distinguishable.

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